

**DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES, REQUIREMENTS AND FACTORS FOR
IMPROVING THE FORMATION OF MORAL AND CULTURAL RELATIONS
IN FUTURE TEACHERS**

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Annotation: Scientific research dedicated to shaping and educating the consciousness, worldview, and thinking of the younger generation on the basis of enlightenment emphasizes the effective use of the educational ideas of great scholars who made invaluable contributions to the development of world science. In the process of acquiring knowledge, expanding worldview and intellectual potential plays a practical and decisive role, and is regarded as a key pedagogical factor that determines the future.

Keywords: Spirituality, ethics and etiquette, enlightenment, modern culture, economy, science, technology, justice, honesty, sincerity, conscience, honor and dignity, patriotism.

The development of various branches of science in our land testifies to the region's rich cultural, spiritual, and economic potential, as well as the intellectual potential of our people, and also allows us to imagine the significant contribution of our thinkers to the development of Islamic sciences and Muslim culture.

There are many definitions of spirituality. Finding a precise and concise answer to the question "What is spirituality?" is not easy. Thinkers, political scientists, statesmen, public figures, and educational scientists have expressed various opinions on this matter.

The concept of "spirituality" in a broad sense is a socio-spiritual phenomenon that encompasses ideological, ideological, educational, cultural, religious, and moral views present in society.

This definition reflects all spiritual aspects of human activity. According to A. Erkaev, "Spirituality is the essence of man as a socio-cultural being, that is, the sum total of such human qualities as mercy, justice, honesty, sincerity, conscience, honor, patriotism, the pursuit of beauty, hatred of evil, will, courage, and many other innate virtues."

M. Imomnazarov writes: "Spirituality is the divine light in the human heart... spirituality is the light of truth reflected in the mirror of the human soul. To give another definition would be to limit this boundless essence."

T. Makhmudov gives the following definition: "...Spirituality is a concept expressing a certain level of physical, intellectual, moral, and spiritual development and worldview of a person."

Morality and etiquette form the basis of spirituality.

The word "akhloq" (morality) in Arabic means behavior, character, and manners. The term "morality" also expresses the meaning of morality. Translated from Greek, "ethos" means custom, behavior, or tradition. Aristotle used it as a synonym for morality.

The word "odob" (etiquette, manners) reflects the external and internal aspects of cultural behavior. It manifests itself in actions and relationships between people (in the family, at work, etc.).

Abu Nasr Farabi said: "Just as the maturity of a tree is determined by its fruit, so all human qualities are culminated in moral education."

Researchers distinguish three elements of morality: moral consciousness, moral feelings, and moral relationships (moral actions).

Without these three elements, it is impossible to imagine morality. In other words, moral relationships cannot exist without feelings and awareness.

Understanding the rules of morality helps a person distinguish between what is permitted and what is not, and how one should live.

Moral consciousness is the sum of people's views and ideas about norms of behavior, principles, responsibilities, and relationships in society.

Morality is formed through an awareness of moral views.

The content and essence of morality and etiquette determine their role in the life and development of society.

Education is the unity of training and upbringing: training imparts knowledge, and upbringing imparts the ability to apply it in practice.

Education eliminates dependence, fear, and uncertainty, bestowing spiritual strength and enormous potential on a person. Therefore, freedom fighters of all times believed that the independence of the state and the people lies in the spiritual awakening of society.

Great scholars such as Ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, Ulugbek, Bukhari, Termizi, Margiloni, Moturidi, Zamakhshari, and others not only reached the heights of scholarship but also widely disseminated knowledge and educated students.

The Turkestan school of education has a rich history. Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdullah Avloni, Mahmudkhozha Behbudi, and others believed that the only way to rid the people of ignorance was through education.

Avloni's words, "Knowledge is the support, life, guidance, and salvation of man," became the motto of this movement.

Mahmudkhozha Behbudi rightly noted, "To live in peace, it is necessary to master secular knowledge; a people deprived of modern sciences will inevitably fall under the oppression of others," a fact confirmed by time and technological advances.

It is essential to remember the hadith: "Do not forget the Hereafter for the sake of this world, and do not forget this world for the sake of the Hereafter," as spiritual and secular knowledge have always complemented each other.

Bahauddin Naqshband coined the motto: "The heart is with God, the hands are in labor."

The teachings of the Naqshbandi tariqa were later systematized by his student Muhammad Porso.

Khoja Akhror significantly expanded the social foundation of the tariqa and strengthened its influence, making it accessible to all strata of society.

Later, this term began to be used figuratively—as education, good breeding.

Conclusion

The concept of culture is a multifaceted and broad social phenomenon. Despite numerous studies devoted to the study of culture, there remains no single, universally accepted definition. Во многих научных трудах подчеркивается, что количество определений культуры превышает 500.

Considering that these data relate to the 1980s and 1990s, one can imagine how much their number has increased by today.

It was believed that since culture manifests itself, there was no need to define its essence. If the question was raised, references to history or the present were given, claiming that the issue had already been resolved.

However, today's events, when elements of culture and lack of culture dangerously intermingle, force us, whether we like it or not, to reflect on the essence of true culture and strive to understand it.

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